

The Teachers' Population Data (independent variables)

Experiment (Intervention) Teachers No=25	Gender	Teaching experience (years)	Grades no	Education	Academy institution
	F-20 M-5	Up to 10 (n=12)	7-9 (n=16)	B.A (n=11)	College (n=13) Uni (n=12)
		Up to 20 (n=6)	10-12 (n=6)	M.A (n=12)	
		Above 20 (n=7)	7-12 (n=3)	Ph.D. (n=1)	

Control Teachers No=20	Gender	Teaching experience (Years)	Grades no	Education	Academy institution
	F-16 M-4	Up to 10 (n=9)	7-9 (n=11)	B.A (n=7)	College (n=7) Uni (n=13)
		Up to 20 (n=2)	10-12 (n=7)	M.A (n=11)	
		Above 20 (n=9)	7-12 (n=2)	Ph.D. (n=2)	